

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

**EXPLORE MORE
USE CASES**

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

DUC 1 - Data-driven Strategies for
Invasive Species Management

Funded by
the European Union

From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and proposes an integrated, evidence-based solution.

DUC 1 focuses on the invasive species management.

Marine Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) are a major threat to marine ecosystems and biodiversity across Europe. Early detection, forecasting, and rapid response are essential tools to prevent their spread. This DUC focuses on using genetic monitoring, citizen science, and environmental data to provide **early warnings and predictive models** for managing NIS in Europe's coastal regions.

Challenge

Invasive marine species often go undetected until it's too late.

Limited data and unclear response strategies often hinder effective action. Environmental agencies need **timely, evidence-based guidance** to detect, track, assess, and respond to biological invasions.

Solution

This DUC proposes an integrated approach to detect, predict and manage marine invasions.

The combined data sources help identify invasion hotspots, trace transmission pathways, and predict spreading vectors, providing timely, actionable insights to support faster and more targeted responses.

Data and monitoring networks used

Genetic observatories (EMO BON), citizen science, systematic monitoring, environmental data, and socio-economic data (from e.g. traffic, ports, marinas)

Bio-ORACLE

HELCOM

Expected Outputs

Biogeographic maps

Early warning alerts

Management recommendations

The use case also highlights essential Digital Twin capabilities.

- **Event anticipation:** Early detection and rapid response to NIS
- **Gap analysis:** Reveals missing data and analytical limitations within biodiversity monitoring flows

Useful for

- **Environmental agencies:** municipalities, county councils, port and marine authorities
- **Public bodies reporting** under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and implementing the Ballast Water Management Convention (BWMC)

Learn more on development and read the publications

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

Consortium

Subscribe to our Newsletter!

@DTOBioFlow @DTOBioFlowProject company/dto-bio-flow

Funded by the European Union